

Full Length Research Paper

Haematology and Serum Biochemistry of Castrated West African Dwarf buck Fed Varying Levels of Local Brewers' Dried Grain With Ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) Leaves Basal Diets

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This study was conducted to determine the effects of feeding West African Dwarf goats varying levels of Brewers' dried grain and Ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) as basal diet on Haematology and serum biochemistry. The experimental diets were ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) as basal diet, supplemented with local brewers' dried grain at (0, 50, 100 and 150 g) designated as treatments T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ respectively. These diets were fed to the experimental animals for a period of 63 days. At the end of the experiment, blood samples were collected from the animals through the jugular veins for determination of haematological and serum biochemical parameters. Data obtained were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in a Randomized Complete Block Design using SAS (2001) package and significant differences separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test. Results showed that PCV, Hb, RBC,

WBC, MCHC, MCH and MCV ranged from 34.00 - 44.50%, 8.00 - 11.17 g/dl, 12.00 - 14.00, 8.40-9.60 x10³/mm³, 2.14 - 2.58 x10⁶/mm³, 3.57- 6.74 fL. Blood serum protein ranges were (6.00 -7.10), Albumin (4.10 - 5.20), Globulin (4.70 - 5.30), Glucose (62.00 - 56.50) and Blood urea of 7.60 - 8.70 respectively. The values for serum enzymes were (7.50 - 8.80), (7.10 - 8.30) (8.67 - 10.40) in that order. Other blood indices (MCV, MCH and MCHC), were within the normal ranges indicating that the goats were not anaemic. It was therefore concluded that Ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) could be used safely to fatten goats as basal diet supplemented with brewers' dried grain during the critical dry period of the year.

Keywords: Haematology , serum biochemistry, West African Dwarf goats, Ber leaves, brewers' dried grain

INTRODUCTION

It is seldom realized that probably more animals feed on shrub and tree fodder than on grasses. Fodder trees are also nutritious like leguminous fodder crop (Akram *et al.*, 2010). Tree leaves play an important role in the nutrition

of grazing animals in areas where few or no alternatives are available (Meuret *et al.*, 2010). Trees forages are used as protein and energy sources for small ruminant (Singh *et al.*, 2009) because the secondary plant compounds

(Tannins) present in tree leaves, enables the ruminants to receive higher levels of dietary protein at post rumen for digestion and absorption. It is attributed that trees play great role in supplying dietary nitrogen, energy, mineral, and vitamins in arid and semi-arid region (Cherry et al., 2007; Huar and Sadulla, 2008). Fodder tree leaves are an alternative source of livestock feeding and tree leaves have the potential for alleviating some of the feed shortages and nutritional deficiencies for small ruminant and important component of goats and sheep diets (Kamalak et al., 2004). This is so because fodder trees are an important source of supplementary protein, vitamins and minerals in developing countries (Singh et al., 2009).

Gutteridge and Shelton, (1996) reported that forage from tree legumes is often used as a buffer to overcome feed gaps that arise from seasonal fluctuations in the productivity of other feed sources. Grasses and herbs may die when upper soil layers lose their moisture but the deep-rooted trees exploit moisture at depth and continue to grow. During the dry season or in times of drought, trees provide green forage rich in protein, minerals and vitamins while the herbaceous cover provides only poor quality straw.

According to Adeloye, (1998) goat production in Nigeria makes a major contribution to the agrarian economy. The author further reported that the West African Dwarf goats are found in the region, south of latitude 14°N across West Africa in the coastal area which is humid and favours high prevalence of diseases. Though this eco-zone is infested with tsetse flies, this breed of goats thrive well here and reproduce with twins and triplet births, thereby satisfying a part of the meat requirement in this region. The use of blood indices is an important medium to ascertain the health, nutritional and physiological status of animals (WHO, 2003). Mbassa and Poulsen, (2003) reported that variations in blood parameters of animals are due to several factors such as altitude, feeding level, age, sex, breed, diurnal and seasonal variation, temperature and physiological status of animals.

Inadequate nourishment triggers mobilization of body reserves, loss of weight, and body condition score (BCS) (Chimonyo et al., 2002). Blood metabolites are important indicators of nutritional status that change profile even before alterations in body weights are observed (Olafadehan, 2011). Blood biochemistry gives a reliable and consolidated measure of the sufficiency of dietary nutrients that can be used regardless of the physiological state of the animal (Pambu-Gallah et al., 2000). Metabolites that reflect an animal's protein status include: albumin, globulin, total protein (TP), creatinine, and urea (Dampsey et al., 2014). Albumin concentration decreases when an animal is exposed to deficiencies in dietary protein or parasitism (Ndlovu et al., 2009; Mapiye et al., 2010). Compromised nourishment leads to the mobilization of muscle which is shown by reduced body

condition, loss of weight, an increase in blood urea (Chimonyo et al., 2002) and low creatinine concentration (Daramola et al., 2005). On the other hand, negative energy balance leads to lipid metabolism resulting in elevated concentrations of non-esterified fatty acids and β -hydroxybutyrate (Dampsey et al., 2014). Determination of metabolic blood profiles, including serum mineral and biochemical parameters are necessary to study ruminant metabolism disorders.

Nutritional adequacy to the goats can be evaluated using blood, daily weight gains; body condition scores (BCS) and carcass characteristics. Information on Haematology and serum biochemistry of intact West African Dwarf bucks fed varying levels of local brewers' dried grain with ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) leaves basal diets is scanty. The research was therefore carried out to bridge this gap.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

The experiment was conducted at the Livestock Teaching and Research Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Adamawa State University Mubi, Nigeria. Mubi is located in the Northern part of Adamawa State. It lies on Latitude 9°11' north of the equator and Longitude 13°45' east of the Greenwich Meridian at an altitude of 696 m above sea level. It is bounded in the South and East by Republic of Cameroun. The State has a land area of 4,728.77 m² and population of 245,460 (Saidu and Gadiga, 2004), it is situated in the Sudan Savanna zone of Nigeria. The vegetation type is best described as *Combretaceous* woodland savanna (Areola, 1983) which consists of grasses or weeds and shrubs collectively making 70% of the entire vegetation. Some of these grasses, weeds and shrubs are used as animal feeds. The area has two distinct seasons; Rainy season lasts for four (4) months and dry season that lasts for eight (8) months. Annual rainfall ranges from 700-900 mm with highest peak in August. The area has minimum temperature of 12.7°C in January and maximum of 37°C in April (Adebayo, 2004).

Sources of feed ingredients

Feed ingredients were obtained from two different sources in and around Mubi environs. The ber (*Ziziphus jujube*) leaves were obtained from the wild by lopping the trees, collecting, drying under the shades and bagging the leaves. Local Brewers' dried grain was bought from the local beer brewers.

Experimental animals and management

The experimental animals were bought from local markets in and around Mubi and Michika Local

Government area, Adamawa State, Nigeria. Twelve (12) West African Dwarf (WAD) bucks with average age of Twelve (12) months weighing 13 (± 0.7) kg were used for the experiments. The animals were castrated using burdizzo, then individually housed in wooden pens measuring 1.50m² floor spaces and height of 1.50m. The floor was made of concrete and covered with wood shavings to conserve heat and absorb animal urine. All the animals were dewormed, treated against ectoparasites; Beranil was used against hemoparasites and antibiotics were administered. At the end of the adaptation/acclimatization period of one week, they were tagged and randomly allocated to different experimental diets using completely randomized block design. They were weighed to obtain initial weights and balanced for the weights before embarking on data collection. There were four (4) treatments each replicated three times making twelve (12) experimental animals.

Experimental design and duration

The experimental diets consisted of ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) as basal diet, supplemented with local brewers' dried grain at 0 g, 100 g, 150 g and 200 g designated as treatments T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄ as indicated in (Table 1). These diets were fed to the animals throughout the experimental period of 63 days. At the end of the experimental period, harness bags were used in collecting faecal droppings to determine apparent digestibility of the test diets.

Data collection and analysis

Ten (10) mls of blood samples were collected from two bucks in each treatment using sterile syringe and needle and then sent to haematology laboratory for haematological studies and chemical pathology laboratory for biochemical analysis in Adamawa State University Clinic Mubi. Three (3) mls of the blood was placed in a sterile sample bottle containing ethylene diamine tetracetic acid (EDTA) for haematological studies and the remaining 7mls (without anticoagulant) was used for blood chemistry (serum metabolites) determination. The blood for Haematology was deposited in EDTA sample bottle that was gently rolled to ensure no hemagglutination and proper mixture with the anticoagulant (EDTA) while that for biochemistry was in plain sample bottle. The haematological parameters determined were packed cell volume (PCV), Red blood cell counts (RBC) and White blood cell counts (WBC) as described by Coles (1986). Haemoglobin content was determined by cyanmt haemoglobin method (Coles, 1986).

Blood urea concentration was determined by Nessler reaction (Tanis and Naylor, 1986). Serum total protein

was estimated by the Biuret method as described by Nicole and Allen, (1985). Albumin was estimated by Bromo cresol green (BCG) method (Peter *et al.*, 1982) whereas globulin concentration was determined by difference between total protein and albumin. Blood glucose was determined by glucose oxidase method (Stone, 1954). Serum enzymes; Alanine transaminase (ALT) and Aspartate transaminase (AST) were determined according to the methods of (Olafadehan, 2011) and the metabolites (urea and Creatinine) were determined as described by Eun *et al.* (2009). Glucose was estimated in the plasma using enzymatic methods in which NAE2-27 reagent was used following oxidation with glucose oxidase. A Chexcks machine (Next/Vetex Alfa Wasseman Analyser, Woerden, Netherlands) and commercially available kits (Siemens Proprietary Limited, Midrand, and South Africa) were used to analyze serum. Serum was analyzed spectrophotometrically for creatinine, total protein (TP) and albumin using colorimetric methods. Urea analysis was done using enzymatic methods. Globulin concentration was computed by subtracting albumin concentration from TP, whereas albumin-globulin ratio was calculated by dividing albumin concentration by that of globulin. Ultra violet methods were used to determine activity of creatine kinase.

Data analysis

Data obtained were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using a Randomized Complete Block Design using SAS (2001). Where significant differences occurred among means, Duncan Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) was used to separate them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the experimental diets, the proximate compositions of experimental diets are presented in (Table 2). The crude protein levels of supplemental feed (brewers' dried grain BDG) being 19.61% and basal feed *Ziziphus jujube* (16.10 %) are high enough to meet the nutritional requirements of goats (Devendra and Burns, 1995). However, the crude fiber levels are lower than that required by the animals (Devendra and Burns, 1995). Bhatta *et al.* (2005) reported that although fodder trees are often valuable sources of dietary protein and energy for livestock in semi-arid regions, maximum nutritional and economic benefits could be harvested, if used as supplement rather than as a sole feed. Ghulam *et al.* (2013) found that tree leaves successfully replaced 50% concentrate in the ration of growing goats.

Haematological indices

Effects of the diets on haematology of the animals are shown in (Table 3). Results showed that PCV, Hb, RBC,

Table 1. Composition of experimental diets.

Feeds	Treatments			
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄
BDG (g)	0	50	100	150
BL	ad lib	ad lib	ad lib	ad lib
Salt (NaCl)%	2	2	2	2

Table 2. Proximate Compositions of experimental feeds

Parameters	Brewers' dried grain (BDG)	Ber leaves (<i>Ziziphus jujube</i>)
Dry matter (DM) %	9.00	85.79
Crude protein (CP) %	19.61	16.10
Crude fiber (CF) %	15.82	11.04
Ether extract (EE) %	6.50	4.40
Ash %	9.2	9.2

Table 3. Effects of diets on Haematological indices of castrated West African Dwarf bucks

Parameters	Treatments				SEM	Sig Lev
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄		
PCV (%)	37.50 ^c	34.00 ^d	44.50 ^a	41.00 ^b	0.92	**
Hb (g/dl)	9.50 ^c	8.00 ^d	11.17 ^a	10.17 ^b	0.32	**
RBC (X ¹² ul)	13.50 ^{ab}	12.00 ^b	13.97 ^{ab}	14.00 ^a	0.38	**
WBC (X ¹⁰ L)	8.70 ^b	8.40 ^b	9.60 ^a	8.60 ^b	0.16	**
MCV (fl)	4.44 ^b	3.57 ^c	6.74 ^a	3.95 ^c	0.09	**
MCH pg	11.45 ^c	13.86 ^b	14.42 ^a	8.45 ^d	0.11	**
MCHC (g/l)	2.58	2.44	2.14	2.34	0.12	NS

WBC, MCHC, MCH and MCV ranged from 34.00 – 44.50 %, 8.00 – 11.17 g/dl, 12.00 – 14.00 x10³mm³, 8.40-9.60 x10³/mm³, 2.14 – 2.58 x10⁶/mm³, 8.45-14.42 and 3.57-6.74 fL, respectively. There were significant (p<0.05) differences across treatments in haematological indices of goats except for mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCHC) concentration. Goats fed 150g brewers' dried grain (T₃) had significantly lower mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) values as compared with other treatment groups. Haemoglobin range was in the normal range of 8-12g/dl (Kaneko *et al.*, 1997) and 9.5g/dl (Opara *et al.*, 2010). The PCV values of T₁ and T₂ were similar to the ranges of 21-31% for healthy goats reported by Daramola *et al.* (2005). Those of treatments T₃ and T₄ (44.50 and 41.00) were higher than those reported by Daramola *et al.* (2005) who stated that packed cell volume (PCV) indicates relative proportions of plasma and red blood cell of the animal. That white blood cell counts are indicators of immune response to foreign bodies in the organism.

Serum proteins

Effects of the diets on serum proteins are shown in (Table 4). Blood serum protein ranges were total protein

(6.00 -7.10), Albumin (4.10 – 5.20), Globulin (4.70 – 5.30), Glucose (62.00 – 56.50) and Blood urea of 7.60 – 8.70 respectively. Similarly, for the blood serum chemistry, there were significant (p<0.05) differences for all the parameters across treatments. With the exception of albumin, treatment (T₃) had the highest values for the parameters. The blood protein ranges of 6.00 to 7.10 g/dl were similar to 5.2 g/dl reported by Daramola *et al.* (2005) healthy West African dwarf bucks. The values for albumin and globulin 4.10-5.20 and 4.70-5.30g/dl were higher than the 2.8 g/dl and 2.4 g/dl normal values reported by Opara *et al.* (2010).

Serum enzymes

Effects of the diets on serum enzymes are shown in (Table 5). The values for serum enzymes were AST (7.50 -8.80), ALT (7.10 – 8.30), Bilirubin (8.67 – 10.40) and blood urea (7.60 – 8.70) in that order. Serum enzymes, Blood urea, Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and AST all differed significantly (p<0.05) across treatment except that of AST. Values obtained were not far from the 6.7 IU/l and 5.3 iu/l reported by Opara *et al.* (2010) for healthy West African dwarf bucks. These results were obtained because *Ziziphus jujube* leaves have low

Table 4. Effects of diets on serum proteins

Parameter	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	SEM	Lev. Sig
Tot. Proteins (g/dl)	6.37 ^b	6.90 ^{ab}	7.10 ^a	6.00 ^b	0.14	**
Album (g/dl)	4.10 ^b	4.17 ^b	5.10 ^{ab}	5.20 ^a	0.09	**
Globulin(g/dl)	4.90 ^b	4.70 ^b	4.87 ^b	5.30 ^a	0.12	**

SEM=Standard Error of the Mean.

Table 5. Effects of diets on serum enzymes and metabolites

Parameter	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	SEM	Lev. sig
Blood Urea (mg/dl)	8.01 ^{bc}	7.60 ^c	8.70 ^a	8.30 ^b	0.14	**
AST (IU/l)	8.60 ^{ab}	7.67 ^b	7.50 ^b	8.80 ^a	0.25	NS
ALT (IU/l)	7.50 ^b	7.10 ^b	7.70 ^b	8.30 ^a	0.23	**
Glucose (mg/dl)	59.00 ^{ab}	56.50 ^b	62.00 ^a	61.50 ^{ab}	1.82	**
Bilirubin (g/dl)	8.70 ^c	8.67 ^c	10.40 ^a	9.40 ^b	0.30	**

SEM=Standard Error of the Mean

abc: Means with different superscripts within a row are significantly different (P<0.05), SEM: Standard Error of Means.

condensed tannins (Brown *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, Makkar *et al.* (1993) had earlier reported that generally, animals consuming tannin-rich feeds develop defensive mechanisms by secreting proteins in their saliva.

Conclusion

The results of the research showed that Haemoglobin range was in the normal range of 8-12g/dl, PCV ranges of 21-31%, blood protein ranges similar to 5.2g/dl, Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and AST values obtained were not far from the normal 6.7 IU/l and 5.3 IU/l. Therefore the experimental diets had no adverse effects on haematological and biochemical indices of indigenous West African Dwarf goats. It can then be concluded that Ber leaves (*Ziziphus jujube*) could be used safely to fatten goats as basal diet supplemented with brewers' dried grain especially during the critical dry period of the year.

Authors' Declaration

We declare that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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